

Open Science markers in research publications of SciLifeLab infrastructure units, open test version

Version 2

Description

This data management plan contains a collection of datasets with Open Science markers that were collected through a manual analysis of research publications of different infrastructure units of SciLifeLab. These markers answer the questions:

1. Is a research publication is accessible through open access?
2. Does a research publication contains a data availability statement?
3. Which ways did researchers choose to give access to the research data that are the basis for the results that they publish? For instance, do the researchers apply the FAIR-guiding principles and describe their data with metadata profiles in trusted repositories or do they add them as supplementary data to their publications?

Funder

Umeå University Library

Grant

Internal funding by Umeå

University Library

Researchers

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Organizations

Umeå University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Open Science markers in research publications of SciLifeLab infrastructure units, open test version](#)

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Umeå University Library](#)

Grants: [Internal funding by Umeå University Library](#)

Project: [Open Science markers in research publications](#)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Markers of Open Science in publications of the Swedish Chemical Biology Consortium (CBCS)

This is a description of a dataset of a study of Open Science markers in research publications of SciLifeLab infrastructure units. The dataset contains markers of Open Science in publications of the Swedish Chemical Biology Consortium (CBCS).

Template: [Swedish Research Council](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Description of data – reuse of existing data and/or production of new data

1.2 Description of data – reuse of existing data and/or production of new data

1.2.2 How will data be collected, created or reused?

1.2.2.2 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

This dataset contains markers of Open Science in the publications of the Chemical Biology Consortium Sweden (CBCS) between 2010 and July 2023. The sample of CBCS publications during this period consists of 188 articles. The researcher visited every publication manually at its DOI URL to answer the following questions. 1. Is the research article an Open Access publication? 2. Does the research article have a Creative Common license or a similar license? 3. Does the research article contain a data availability statement? 4. Did the authors submit data of their study to a repository such as EMBL, Genbank,

Protein Data Bank PDB, Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre CCDC, Dryad, or a similar repository? 5. Does the research article contain supplementary data? 6. Do the supplementary data have a persistent identifier that makes them citable as a defined research output? In this project the dataset by Kieselbach (2023) will be re-used and new data from publications after June 2023 will added. Reference: Kieselbach, Theresa (2023). Analysis of CBCS publications for Open Access, data availability statements and persistent identifiers for supplementary data. Umeå University. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.17044/scilifelab.23641749.v1>

1.2.2.3 What is the origin of the data?

Publications of the Chemical Biology Consortium Sweden at URL: <https://publications.scilifelab.se/label/Chemical%20Biology%20Consortium%20Sweden%20%28CBCS%29>

1.2.3 What types of data will be created and/or collected, in terms of data format and amount/volume of data?

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Created

Text, spreadsheet data

.txt, .xlsx, .csv

< 1GB

2 Documentation and data quality

2.3 Documentation and data quality

2.3.2 How will the material be documented and described, with associated metadata relating to structure, standards and format for descriptions of the content, collection method, etc.?

2.3.2.2 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

- RDF Data Cube Vocabulary

- CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)
- Dublin Core
- DataCite Metadata Schema

other

Comment:

METS, UKETD_DC

2.3.2.3 URL/Location

a. <https://figshare.scilifelab.se/>

SciLifeLab Data Repository

b. <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

Metadata Standards Catalog

2.3.2.4 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Comment:

No additional standardized vocabularies will be used.

2.3.2.6 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

2.3.2.7 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

not listed

2.3.2.8 URL/Name

<https://figshare.scilifelab.se/>

SciLifelab Data Repository

2.3.3 How will data quality be safeguarded and documented (for example repeated measurements, validation of data input, etc.)?

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Defined folder structure, Consistent, descriptive file names (e. g.: Project_Description_Researcher_Date_version) Version control of files, File format and software description, Integrity check of data files, Comply with the Policy for Research data at Umeå University

3 Storage and backup

3.4 Storage and backup

3.4.2 How is storage and backup of data and metadata safeguarded during the research process?

3.4.2.2 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Comment:

OneDrive at Umeå University,

Hard disc drive on work computer

3.4.3 How is data security and controlled access to data safeguarded, in relation to the handling of sensitive data and personal data, for example?

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In this study, no sensitive data will be used. The storage facilities comply with the requirements for work with common personal data.

3.4.3.3 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Delete at end of project

Comment:

Data of limited use are work material that does not have to be preserved and archived.

4 Legal and ethical aspects

4.5 Legal and ethical aspects

4.5.2 How is data handling according to legal requirements safeguarded, e.g. in terms of handling of personal data, confidentiality and intellectual property rights?

This study does not need other personal data than those that are needed for administration of the research project. It does not use any content that is secret or protected by intellectual property rights either.

4.5.3 How is data handling according to legal requirements safeguarded, e.g. in terms of handling of personal data, confidentiality and intellectual property rights?

Please see 4.1.1

5 Accessibility and long-term storage

5.6 Accessibility and long-term storage

5.6.2 How, when and where will research data or information about data (metadata) be made accessible? Are there any conditions, embargoes and limitations on the access to and reuse of data to be considered?

5.6.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

all

5.6.3 In what way is long-term storage safeguarded, and by whom? How will the selection of data for long-term storage be made?

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Departmental archive

The staff responsible for the departmental archive

5.6.3.3 How will the selection of data for long-term storage be made?

The PI will curate the data that are going to be preserved.

5.6.4 Will specific systems, software, source code or other types of services be necessary in order to understand, partake of or use/analyse data in the long term?

5.6.4.2 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

Yes

5.6.4.3 Please provide links describing the methods for accessing the data.

The data files can be opened and used with an up-to-date Windows computer and Office software

5.6.4.4 Please provide links describing the tools for accessing the data.

Microsoft Office

5.6.4.5 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

For some data

5.6.4.6 Please describe which data require proprietary tools to access the data?

Excel spreadsheets and Word documents need Microsoft Office software.

5.6.5 How will the use of unique and persistent identifiers, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), be safeguarded?

5.6.5.2 Persistent identifiers

DOI

6 Responsibility and resources

6.7 Responsibility and resources

6.7.2 Who is responsible for data management and (possibly) supports the work with this while the research project is in progress? Who is responsible for data management, ongoing management and long-term storage after the research project has ended?

6.7.2.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment:

The PI will be the data manager.

6.7.2 What resources (costs, labour input or other) will be required for data management (including storage, back-up, provision of access and processing for long-term storage)? What resources will be needed to ensure that data fulfil the FAIR principles?

6.7.2.2 What resources (costs, labour input or other) will be required for data management (including storage, back-up, provision of access and processing for long-term storage)?

The cost for labor, storage, back-up and long-term storage are covered by Umeå University and by the SciLifeLab Data Centre.

6.7.2.3 What resources will be needed to ensure that data fulfill the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles?

The SciLifeLab Data Repository will be used to create metadata profiles that comply with the recommendations of the FAIR-data principles.

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